

1 **Therapeutic targeting in breast cancer for the treatment of lung metastasis: UTP4.**

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6 Metastasis is the major cause of death from cancer and metastasis to the lung in breast cancer is difficult
7 to treat and heterogeneous in nature, complicating its management (1-5). We recently utilized whole
8 transcriptome technologies to define the full complement of differentially expressed kinases and
9 phosphatases in HER2+ breast cancer: in the primary tumor, and in metastasis to the CNS (6-8). Here we
10 utilize whole transcriptome technologies (9, 10) to measure total transcription in the lung metastases of
11 humans with breast cancer, integrating this with transcriptome data from a cell culture model of lung
12 metastatic potential. We identify here a therapeutic target based on its differential expression and
13 up-regulation upon metastasis to the lung in humans with breast cancer, UTP4, as a candidate therapeutic
14 target for the medical management of lung metastasis.
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We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lungs to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the lung metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: UTP4.

Results

Figure 1: UTP4 is differentially expressed in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Cell culture model of lung metastatic propensity; human breast cancer.

n=2 MDA-PAR lung metastasis cancer cells (MDA-MB-231, low metastatic potential)

n=2 MDA-LM2 lung metastasis cancer cells (MDA-MB-231, high metastatic potential)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
84916	1.02E-01	0.244	-1.636332	-0.399564	148.2	UTP4	1353/10554	87.2

Through measurement of total transcription in cells with low metastatic potential as compared to cells with high metastatic potential using the MDA-LM2 model derived from MDA-MB-231 breast cancer cells, we discovered differential expression of UTP4 in metastasis to the lung in breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of UTP4 changed more than 85% of the lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 10,554 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating higher expression of UTP4 messenger RNA in breast cancer cells with high potential to metastasize to the lungs, demonstrating viability of UTP4 as a therapeutic target to manage disease progression and dissemination to the lungs in humans with breast cancer.

II. Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
84916	3.19E-02	0.435	-2.146221	-0.9344223	811.36	UTP4	3344/22997	85.5

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of UTP4 small subunit processome component, encoded by *UTP4* in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 2**). The expression of UTP4 changed more than 85% of the human lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of UTP4 messenger RNA in lung metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of UTP4 during disease progression and dissemination in breast cancer.

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2 Thus, differential and increased expression of UTP4 defines the lung metastatic transcriptome in
3 human breast cancer.

4 **Discussion**

5 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
6 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
7 trastuzumab). Inhibitors of UTP4, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for toxicity
8 and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with lung metastasis who have failed
9 previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of lung metastasis in
10 humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose
11 metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase
12 approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the
13 daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding
14 cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone
15 resistance (11).
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References

1. Minn, A.J., Gupta, G.P., Siegel, P.M., Bos, P.D., Shu, W., Giri, D.D., Viale, A., Olshen, A.B., Gerald, W.L. and Massagué, J., 2005. Genes that mediate breast cancer metastasis to lung. *Nature*, 436(7050), pp.518-524.
2. Zardavas, D., Irrthum, A., Swanton, C. and Piccart, M., 2015. Clinical management of breast cancer heterogeneity. *Nature reviews Clinical oncology*, 12(7), pp.381-394.
3. Poste, G., Tzeng, J., Doll, J., Greig, R., Rieman, D. and Zeidman, I., 1982. Evolution of tumor cell heterogeneity during progressive growth of individual lung metastases. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 79(21), pp.6574-6578.
4. Minn, A.J., Gupta, G.P., Padua, D., Bos, P., Nguyen, D.X., Nuyten, D., Kreike, B., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y., Ishwaran, H. and Foekens, J.A., 2007. Lung metastasis genes couple breast tumor size and metastatic spread. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 104(16), pp.6740-6745.
5. Brown, D.M. and Ruoslahti, E., 2004. Metadherin, a cell surface protein in breast tumors that mediates lung metastasis. *Cancer cell*, 5(4), pp.365-374.
6. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Increased rate of CNS metastasis in patients with HER2+ breast cancer is a result of the intrinsic gene expression program of HER2+ subtype breast cancers, not a consequence of use of the HER2+-targeted drug trastuzumab.
7. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Kinase targeting in HER2+ breast cancer to prevent and treat CNS disease: CDK8.
8. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: PPP1R3D.
9. GSE191230: Ong, L.T., Lee, W.C., Ma, S., Oguz, G., Niu, Z., Bao, Y., Yusuf, M., Lee, P.L., Goh, J.Y., Wang, P. and Yong, K.S.M., 2022. IFI16-dependent STING signaling is a crucial regulator of anti-HER2 immune response in HER2+ breast cancer. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 119(31), p.e2201376119.
10. GSE186637: "Comparing alternative polyadenylation landscapes in highly and poorly metastatic breast cancer cells." Albertas N, Hosseinali A, Juliane W, Lisa F, Kristle G, Hani G. University of California, San Francisco (UCSF). Biochemistry and Biophysics. San Francisco, CA, USA.
11. Mamoor, Shahan. 2024. Therapeutic targeting of catalytically available solid tumor vulnerabilities in human cancer.

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Methods

We utilized GSE186637 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in human breast cancer cells with high and low lung metastatic potential (along with GSE191230, whole transcription in metastasis to the lungs and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer for target validation) using microarray data and RNA-sequencing (public and published) and R-based computational methods.